

Secure Onboarding Of Devices And Applications to a Smart Decentralized Ecosystem

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Abstract—Data Confidence Fabrics (DCFs) are emerging as a mechanism to obtain measurable trust in decentralized smart computing environments, while remote attestation (RA) is being established as a key mechanism for verifying security in distributed systems. However, both these approaches remain underutilized in container orchestration platforms, resulting in inadequate trust guarantees, increased attack surface areas, and insufficient mechanisms for verifying the integrity of devices and applications. In this paper, we propose leveraging DCFs to integrate RA with software security practices, and utilizing this integration to securely onboard devices and containerized applications by tracing their provenance and analyzing vulnerabilities. This dual-level protection bridges device attestation measurements with measurements of application security to provide measurable and transparent confidence scores for both. The proposed approach brings trustworthiness into a distributed environment where devices are continuously monitored for malicious tampering, and applications are assessed before being run. We verified this approach on a setup representing real environments. Additionally, A machine learning model was put under test and trained on data weighted with confidence scores produced by our proposed approach. The model saw improved performance and accuracy, showing that this approach can increase the reliability of systems.

Index Terms—Secure onboarding, remote attestation, security, distributed systems, smart ecosystems, DCF, software security

I. INTRODUCTION

The proliferation of smart computing has increased the adoption of Internet-of-Things (IoT), edge computing, and cloud-native infrastructures operating beyond well-defined trust boundaries. This has underscored the importance of secure onboarding and continuous integrity monitoring. Secure onboarding refers to the process of integrating new entities into a system in a manner that ensures their authenticity, integrity, and security. This step is critical because compromised or malicious resources can act as entry points for adversaries, threatening the overall security of whole systems [1] [2]. Conventional onboarding techniques often rely on manual configurations or pre-installed credentials, both of which are susceptible to interception or misuse. Secure onboarding, however, employs cryptographic methods, such as digital certificates and zero-touch provisioning to ensure the authenticity of devices such FIDO Device Onboard (FDO) [3]. These mechanisms are increasingly vital in large-scale deployments,

such as IoT ecosystems, where millions of devices must be provisioned securely and autonomously without human intervention.

Secure onboarding derives its principles from Trusted Computing, a set of specifications and concepts established by the Trusted Computing Group (TCG) [4]. Trusted Computing aims to ensure that computer systems consistently behave in expected ways, with these behaviors enforced by both hardware and software. This is achieved through the use of a Trusted Platform Module (TPM), a hardware-based root of trust embedded within modern computing platforms. Central to Trusted Computing is the concept of a hardware-embedded cryptographic identity known as the Endorsement Key (EK), used to securely bind identities and credentials to devices. Additionally, mechanisms such as Sealed Storage ensure sensitive data remains cryptographically protected and inaccessible unless the platform is in a verified, trusted state. Finally, Remote Attestation, a fundamental principle of Trusted Computing, leverages hardware-rooted trust (e.g., TPM) to measure system components and provide cryptographically verifiable evidence of system integrity to external parties.

Remote attestation (RA) complements secure onboarding by providing continuous verification of a device’s state after it has been connected to the system. Remote attestation typically involves a challenge-response protocol where the device generates cryptographically signed evidence of its integrity using a hardware-based root of trust [5]. This process ensures that devices remain trustworthy throughout their operational lifecycle, even in hostile environments. Additionally, security of software applications remains a significant factor for safeguarding systems. A majority of cyber-attacks are conducted through known exploits on software applications [6], which could have been prevented through vulnerability scans and code analysis.

This paper explores the critical role of secure onboarding of both devices and applications to safeguard modern container orchestration platforms. By highlighting existing gaps, this work proposes a novel framework to integrate secure onboarding, remote attestation principles, and software security practices. Through the tools used, measurable confidence in devices and applications is communicated, and further inte-

grated with confidence in the data being generated or transiting through the system.

Contributions. In this paper we (1) securely onboard nodes onto Kubernetes clusters with strong TPM-based identity binding, (2) we propose a framework to quantifiably measure the integrity of devices and workloads and create a link between them (3) we incorporate a scoring system that departs from binary attestation outcomes, either trusted or untrusted, to continuous confidence scores, and finally (4) we provide experiments that quantify the utility of scoring devices, workloads, and data on downstream machine learning model training tasks.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section II provides background and related work, covering trusted computing, remote attestation, and secure onboarding in Kubernetes. Section III details the system design, including architecture and onboarding workflows. Section IV presents the prototype implementation, followed by performance evaluation and an analysis of trust scoring’s impact on machine learning training. Finally, Section V concludes the paper and outlines future directions.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. Trusted Computing

The TPM 2.0 Library Specification [7] defines the TPM as a system component with state separate from its host system, interacting only through a defined interface. It establishes a trusted platform by implementing three Roots of Trust: the Root of Trust for Measurement (RTM), the Root of Trust for Storage (RTS), and the Root of Trust for Reporting (RTR). The RTM records integrity-relevant information by measuring system components and storing their cryptographic hashes in Shielded Locations within the RTS. The RTR retrieves these values, signs them, and provides a report for verification. A concrete example of the application of these concepts is Measured Boot, a process that ensures that boot components have not been tampered with during system startup [8]. Beyond boot-time integrity, the TPM can also be used for runtime integrity monitoring [9]. The OS or security software can extend new measurements post-boot, ensuring that running processes and critical system configurations remain trustworthy. Frameworks like the Linux Integrity Measurement Architecture (IMA) [10] enable continuous verification of system state.

B. TPM-based Remote Attestation

Coker et al. [2] define Remote Attestation as “the activity of making a claim about properties of a *target* by supplying evidence to an *appraiser* over a network”. The work on RA can be split based on the presence or absence of a hardware-based root of trust (such as TPMs) at the *target*. In our work, we assume the former, and thus we focus our scan of the literature on works that anchor trust in hardware components. Terra [11] was one of the earliest systems to use the TPM to enable RA. It supported static attestations allowing virtual machines to prove their initial software stack’s integrity to

remote parties. Sailer et al. [9] extended the concept of RA beyond static measurements, introducing a dynamic integrity measurement architecture for Linux systems that tracks all executable content loaded at runtime. Gu et al. [12] built on the same concept by proposing a mechanism to attest the correctness of a program’s execution by recursively tracking and measuring not only the target’s binary and initial inputs, but also all runtime data dependencies and interactions with other processes.

Many more earlier works have proposed mechanisms to leverage the TPM for attesting the integrity of a target system [13]–[16]. Our exploration of these mechanisms is not meant to be exhaustive, and our work is not aiming at extending them. Rather, and as pinpointed by Coker et al. [2], such mechanisms can be treated as Attestation Service Providers (ASPs) within a composable attestation framework. In this model, an Attestation Manager (AM), running on the *target*, orchestrates a set of ASPs, each of which is responsible for measuring and reporting on a specific aspect of the *target* system’s state to a remote *appraiser*. One system that exemplifies this model is Keylime [17], an RA framework designed to bootstrap and maintain trust in cloud environments. Keylime consists of three main components: the Agent, which runs on each node to collect measurements; the Verifier, which acts as a central authority to periodically check these measurements against expected values and decide whether the node is trustworthy; and the Registrar, which tracks the identity and public keys of all registered nodes. Both Keylime and our proposed system can be mapped to the attestation architecture proposed by Coker et al., with Keylime’s agent acting as both the Attestation Manager and a set of ASPs, while the Cloud Verifier serves as the *appraiser*. However, while Keylime focuses on node-level attestation, our system extends this concept by incorporating workload-level attestation within container orchestration environments (e.g., Kubernetes).

C. Node Bootstrapping in Kubernetes

Kubernetes is an open-source container orchestration platform designed to automate the deployment, scaling, and management of containerized applications across multiple machines. In a Kubernetes cluster, we have control plane nodes that run core components such as the API server, scheduler, and controllers, while worker nodes execute workloads in the form of pods. One of the fundamental security mechanisms in Kubernetes is TLS Bootstrapping [18], which facilitates secure communication between worker nodes and the control plane during node registration. When a new worker node joins the cluster using `kubeadm join`, it undergoes a TLS certificate bootstrapping process, wherein the kubelet authenticates with the API server using a bootstrap token and requests a certificate signing request (CSR). The API server then verifies and signs the request, providing the node with a client certificate that allows it to communicate securely with the control plane. This approach ensures that only authenticated nodes can join the cluster and establish mutual trust via TLS. However, we

highlight three main limitations or attack vectors that this process is susceptible to:

- *Lack of Strong Identity Binding:* Kubernetes relies on bootstrap tokens for authentication during TLS Bootstrapping. If an attacker gains access to an active bootstrap token, they could use it to impersonate a legitimate node.
- *Lack of Verified Boot and Post-Boot Integrity Checks:* TLS Bootstrapping does not verify whether a node has booted securely or whether its firmware, OS, or kubelet binary has been compromised. A malicious actor who gains access to a compromised machine could still use valid credentials to join a cluster.
- *Lack of Runtime Integrity Verification:* TLS Bootstrapping ensures encrypted communication but does not verify whether the running processes on a node remain unchanged. Malicious software could be introduced post-authentication without Kubernetes detecting it.

Some of these limitations have been previously addressed in the literature. The Keylime Attestation-Operator [19] enables automated deployment of Keylime components within Kubernetes. However, its integration alone does not directly address the aforementioned limitations, as it only supports node-level attestation without extending trust guarantees to workloads. The approach presented by Piras et al. [20] addresses this limitation by developing a custom IMA template (`ima-cgpath`) and integrating it with Keylime to discriminate between host-generated and pod-generated events for precise runtime pod-level attestation. Zaritto et al. [21] further expanded this approach by leveraging Keylime within Kubernetes to establish a three-stage attestation framework: Worker Registration, to securely authenticate worker nodes using TPM-based identities; Secure Pod Deployment, to verify the identity and authorization of tenants deploying workloads; and Pod Attestation, to continuously verify pod integrity during runtime by validating TPM quotes and IMA measurements against established whitelists. In this work, we extend these approaches by enhancing identity verification and workload attestation mechanisms and by departing from binary attestation outcomes (trusted/untrusted) to continuous confidence scores.

D. Data Confidence Fabrics

Project Alvarium [22] is an open source initiative that focuses on creating a framework and software development kit (SDK) to build Data Confidence Fabrics (DCF). These fabrics enable the delivery of data from devices to applications with measurable confidence. Alvarium achieves this by publishing attestations, coined *Annotations*, every time data is touched as it moves across the network. This entails that applications performing operations on data are instrumented with the Alvarium SDK in a manner similar to prominent monitoring tools (e.g. Prometheus). Each time data is produced, transformed, or relayed by any application, an annotation attesting to various security features employed on the host device or by the application itself is shared to an external store. These annotations are then consumed by a scoring system that assigns confidence scores to data based on the security,

privacy, and integrity measures applied at each step as the data moved throughout the network. In an earlier work [23] we conducted experiments where machine learning models were trained with a mix of clean and artificially altered “poisoned” data. We demonstrated the utility of confidence scores for mitigating the possibility of poor quality or insecure data sources in datasets. In this work, we extend the scoring system provided by Alvarium to compute context-aware unified trust scores that incorporate device and application-level attestations in container orchestration environments.

E. Software Supply Chain Attestation

Software supply chain attestation addresses the security risks associated with verifying the provenance, integrity, and authenticity of software artifacts before deployment into production environments. Techniques such as Software Bill of Materials (SBOM) [24] and frameworks like the Supply-chain Levels for Software Artifacts (SLSA) [25] mitigate these threats by establishing transparent and cryptographically verifiable records of software origin and build processes. Attestation mechanisms, including container image signing and integrity verification through tools such as Cosign [26] enforce trust policies within container orchestration platforms like Kubernetes. Along the same lines, in our proposed system, we embed a DCF agent directly within CI/CD pipelines. During application builds, this agent publishes annotations containing assessments of application vulnerabilities. The resulting trust scores derived from these annotations are then dynamically linked to the specific nodes on which the applications are deployed.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

At its core, our system builds a Data Confidence Fabric (DCF) by encapsulating TPM-based RA techniques and software supply chain security practices to provide a visible, dual-level measurement of the security posture of both devices and applications in decentralized systems. The choice of DCF annotation types for devices and applications is left to each specific environment and its requirements. However, a fixed staple in our system requires an annotation representing the result of the device identity verification. In order to ensure that the authentication process is trustworthy, a trust anchor should be present in the system. One instantiation of a trust anchor could be a certificate authority that signs the public key generated for the device, which is later uploaded to an onboarding service. For even stronger security, we revert to a hardware root of trust (i.e., TPM) to generate the public key from an unexportable private key assigned to the device. The lack of any trust anchor in the system would result in an unfulfilled identity verification annotation, which should significantly affect the confidence score of a device.

A. Architecture

In this subsection, the components of the reference architecture in Fig. 1 are described, along with their adherence to the RA principles established by Coker et al. [2]. For

Fig. 1: Reference architecture of the proposed secure device and application onboarding.

completeness, we summarize the five principles: *Fresh Information* ensures evidence reflects the current system state; *Comprehensive Information* provides full visibility of the target’s internal state; *Constrained Disclosure* limits information shared with appraisers; *Semantic Explicitness* makes attestation results machine-readable; and *Trustworthy Mechanism* guarantees attestation processes are verifiable and tamper-resistant.

Onboarding Service: This component is a DCF-enabled server that runs on the verifier. It is responsible for detecting newly joined devices, verifying their identities, and publishing relevant annotations. This component strengthens adherence to the *Fresh Information* RA principle by enabling information on devices joining and leaving a network to be immediately available to the verifier.

DCF Agent: The Onboarding Service installs the DCF Agent component onto the target device. The DCF Agent communicates with a trust anchor to seamlessly perform device identity verification with the Onboarding Service. Afterwards, it publishes DCF annotations based on device measurement results, given that it has received permission to do so through the Onboarding Service.

CI/CD Pipeline: A secure CI/CD pipeline enables a DCF agent to monitor and capture information on an application’s build process. DCF Annotations are published based on results of the security state of the applications being built.

DCF Annotations: The published annotations provide a structured way to communicate attestation results. Introducing this mechanism into the secure onboarding space adheres strongly to the *Semantic Explicitness* RA principle by providing deterministic methods to reach the same conclusion about the target device without ad hoc implementation. Moreover, the use of annotations supports the *Trustworthy Mechanism*

RA principle by providing the capability to sign the results using a hardware-based root of trust or other secure mechanisms. The annotations are also the common structure used to communicate both device and application measurements, providing a stronger link between both in the secure onboarding domain.

DCF Scorers: The set of applications that read annotations and provide a policy-driven score for each device or application that has been onboarded by the system. These applications include a DCF Score Calculator which takes annotations as inputs, calculates continuous scores, and persists both in a database. The DCF Score Exporter allows querying confidence scores according to device and application identifiers.

Governing applications can consume the produced confidence score to apply policies, or the consumers of data can decide the best action to take according to the confidence score of the data’s underlying device and application. The combination of DCF scorers and DCF annotations also provides the functionality of an attestation proxy, which obscures device identifiers and information that would be advantageous to adversaries when acquired. Only entities with certain knowledge of a device may query the DCF scorers to obtain its confidence score, and even then, only a score is provided and not the device measurements themselves. This strongly supports the *Constrained Disclosure* RA principle.

B. Device Onboarding Workflow

1) *Device Registration*: The first step in the device onboarding flow occurs out-of-band. The onboarding service is informed of the identity of a device which is expected to join the cluster. This is done through an endpoint on the onboarding service that allows authorized users to upload the certificate of a device that is generated by a trust anchor. Therefore,

Fig. 2: Implementation of device onboarding in a Kubernetes cluster that relies on TPM2 as a trust anchor and Project Alvarium as the DCF of choice. The flow shows Worker Node 2 being onboarded. Steps from 1-5 are shown on the diagram that map to the workflow in the *Device Onboarding Workflow* section.

a trusted user or a secure automated process can generate a cryptographic key pair using a certificate authority or a root of trust and uploads the public key to the onboarding service.

2) *DCF Agent Installation*: When a device first joins the cluster, the onboarding service that is running on the control plane of that cluster can detect this event using the container orchestration platform’s provided APIs. Once the notification of this event is received by the onboarding service, it installs the DCF Agent on the target device.

3) *Device Identity Verification*: Once installed, the DCF agent then sends a request to the onboarding service to get a challenge token, or a nonce, which it will sign with the trust-anchor-generated private key. Once signed, the signature and the challenge token are sent back to the onboarding service for verification using the pre-sent device public key. An annotation is published by the onboarding service to attest the device identity verification process.

4) *Device Security Measurements*: After a device’s identity is verified, the DCF agent begins to analyze multiple security aspects of the device, which should be tailored to the target environment. Examples of the analysis and measurement of these security aspects, per existing remote attestation protocols, include memory validation of embedded devices as implemented in the SWATT protocol [27], or kernel rootkit detection as shown in Pioneer [28].

5) *Scoring*: The DCF scoring apps that reside on the cluster’s control plane calculate a confidence score according to the published annotations. The DCF scorers default to calculating the score through dividing the number of annotations

that passed their checks over the total number of produced annotations. Users may provide a policy by which each annotation is weighted. For example, one user may heavily desire that a device have no unauthorized processes running, while others may prioritize the presence of a non-vulnerable operating system, the annotations representing either aspects are weighted more heavily in the calculation.

C. Application Onboarding Workflow

To securely onboard an application, the DCF monitors the application’s build process. Ideally, this process is automated using a CI/CD pipeline. The DCF agent publishes annotations that contain the measurement results of the application such as vulnerabilities or software supply chain provenance. The annotations are linked to the produced application artifact such as a Docker image.

Similar to the secure device onboarding flow, the DCF scoring applications consume these annotations to produce a confidence score for the application. The score can be queried using an identifier of the produced application artifact. This provides a coherent method to measure and communicate the security status of devices and applications after the onboarding process is complete.

IV. PROTOTYPE IMPLEMENTATION

In this section, we demonstrate the feasibility of our design on applications representing real-world environments using the same components we presented. To do so, the readiness of device confidence scores is measured. This metric represents

Fig. 3: An example of the application security measurements that a Jenkins CI/CD pipeline may conduct. During an application build, annotations are published on the security vulnerabilities, software composition analysis (SCA), and artifact checksum validation.

the time taken for a confidence score of a device to be ready for consumption, and will be compared with the time taken for a device to be configured to join the cluster, and the time taken for the device to be ready to receive and run workloads.

A. Tools

As the environment on which the design is applied to is distributed, Docker and Kubernetes are used as the reference implementations for container runtimes and container orchestration platforms respectively. Devices being onboarded are considered worker nodes joining the Kubernetes cluster, and applications being onboarded are Docker images running on said worker nodes. Moreover, TPM2 is used as the reference for a root of trust, taking the role of the trust anchor proposed in the reference architecture.

The onboarding service is implemented as a REST-based web server. The onboarding service installs the DCF agents as systemd services on each device using Ansible Playbooks, and configures the agents to know the location of the onboarding service which resides on the Kubernetes control plane. All requests to onboard a device are initiated by the DCF agents to the onboarding service. This is an attempt to increase the scalability of the onboarding service and to prevent it from managing the locations and states of multiple devices concurrently.

Additionally, the onboarding service and the DCF agent consume the SDK for Project Alvarium, an implementation of a DCF. A new annotation has been implemented that is published on the successful verification of a device's identity. While this annotation is required by the proposed design, annotations published by the DCF agent are flexible and application-specific.

Fig. 4: Time taken for a node to join a cluster and be ready to accept workloads compared to the time taken for the node's score to be generated and ready for consumption.

A trusted and secure Jenkins CI/CD instance is pre-installed on a Kubernetes cluster, which users can use to build their applications into Docker images, and push them to image repositories. Then, Kubernetes may use the image repository to deploy the application containers on present worker nodes. Moreover, the CI/CD instance imports an Alvarium Shared Library for Jenkins. This library integrates with build pipelines to conduct measurements of applications during the build process and publishes annotations accordingly. Annotations from both the device and the application are made available to the Project Alvarium scoring applications that are deployed on the control-plane.

B. Performance Evaluation

An environment is setup with a 16-node Kubernetes cluster. The cluster's control-plane node, which runs the onboarding service and DCF scorers, contains 16 CPU cores and 64GB of memory. The remaining nodes, which will be running the applications and DCF agents, have a 2GHz CPU with 2 cores each and 4GB of memory. The worker nodes have been removed from the cluster and onboarded using the proposed flow. This process was repeated 10 times and the time taken for each phase has been recorded.

Fig. 4 shows a comparison of the time taken for a device to join the cluster and the time taken to produce a confidence score for the device. In this context, we argue that having a confidence score for a node in 3 additional seconds is an acceptable amount of time to remain adherent to the *Fresh Information* RA principle. Additionally, consequent scores may be produced periodically at shorter intervals. Overall, the

Fig. 5: Setup of multiple farms managed by a single regional service provider, which may be managed by a central global service provider.

result of this experiment shows that our proposed design can work on environments that represent real applications.

However, The result is measured from the start of running the `kubeadm join` command, which includes Preflight checks and TLS Bootstrapping. The time at which a device is available to the cluster but still requiring configuration is pointed out to show that this is when the onboarding service becomes aware of the device, and initiates the onboarding process. Ideally, the onboarding process can be made aware of this event much sooner if integrated with the `kubeadm` client.

C. Impact on Machine Learning Training

In this subsection, we demonstrate the benefits of incorporating the device and application confidence scores produced by our approach in the training of Machine Learning models. We conducted experiments for training and evaluating convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to recognise fresh and rotten fruit. To simulate the presence of false or misleading inputs in data streams, we conducted a data poisoning exercise where, if data is to be poisoned the actual image is replaced by the image of a falsely labeled rotten orange.

In these experiments, an 80/20% training/testing split is conducted on a dataset of 7467 fruits and vegetables (Apples, Bell Peppers, Bananas, Jujubes, Strawberries, Potatoes), and the rotten Oranges used for poisoning come from a different set of 2186 images. The training set is distributed among each of the farm worker nodes and each node has associated device, data, and application scores which are used for evaluating the weighting for each image in training. A variety of device, application, and data scores are present in the farms, though they remain relatively stable across the lifetime of its data reporting – hence individual farms weight their own data roughly equivalently, but the regional and central nodes are able to evaluate data from different farms based on differing scores arising from among their various client farms.

Fig. 6: Model Classification Accuracy, separated by scoring used for weights

Fig. 7: Model Loss, separated by scoring used for weights

These farms share the images with regional nodes which allows these nodes to train a model on a larger volume of data, and to evaluate different weightings based on the security context of different farm devices and applications. Finally, the regional nodes convey the data to the central worker which can avail of all of the data from all farms in training its model, though the impact of potentially compromised data, devices or applications are assessed base on annotation scoring leading to the riskier data contributing much less to the central model’s perception of fruit characteristics, hence, affecting classification performance.

In our results, we observe that the central models perform the best on accuracy and loss metrics – as should be expected as they have access to the largest volume of data – but they

also perform better when scoring is accounted for in model weighting. When the poisoned data is introduced in the data stream, scoring schemes accounting for just data do well, but it is unrealistic for any scheme to expect any particular scheme to be the source of the attack without prior knowledge. As such, the result if "All" in which all annotation and trust sources are accounted for achieves an excellent accuracy and loss result – close to if it were targeted just at the Data vector.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The concept of remote attestation is a well-established foundation for securely onboarding devices. This paper proposes the incorporation of Data Confidence Fabrics to further strengthen the principles of remote attestation by introducing event-driven attestations in the form of annotations, and assigning confidence scores to devices as well as applications. Linking this with existing Data Confidence Fabric concepts, data sent from applications can have its score influenced by that of the application and the device running it. The produced results show the on-time production of device and application confidence scores in real-life environments, allowing the use of confidence scores very briefly after entities are introduced to the system. Furthermore, incorporating the produced device and application confidence scores in machine learning model training showed an improvement in model performance and accuracy over only using data confidence scores, and even more so over not using any confidence scores.

The scoring algorithms used will be further improved to convey more accurate confidence scores according to the information collected through annotations. This may further improve the results shown in this paper. Moreover, the current approach monitors the build process of applications, this will be extended to include the run-time behavior of applications to provide more security measurements over applications.

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